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PROPER NAMES IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract

Literary translation, distinct from technical or legal translation, requires capturing the nuances, emotions, and stylistic elements of the original text. This is particularly challenging when translating proper names, or anthroponyms, which carry significant cultural and emotional weight. Proper names are not just identifiers but also convey deeper meanings and cultural contexts. Translators must balance fidelity to the original text with readability and cultural resonance in the target language, making careful decisions about whether to transliterate, translate, or adapt names.

Azerbaijani poetry, rich in historical and cultural references, underscores the importance of accurate name translation. Names in poetry evoke specific periods, contexts, and emotional responses. The anthology "Anthology of Poetry by Women in Azerbaijan: Classical to Soviet" illustrates this challenge, highlighting the need to preserve the original essence through meticulous transliteration.

Errors in name translation can result in a loss of cultural essence and artistic integrity. Proper names in literature act as semantic markers and carriers of artistic and poetic information. Translators of Azerbaijani poetry strive to adhere to these principles, ensuring that the national essence is effectively conveyed to English-speaking readers.

Keywords: Proper names, transliteration, anthroponym, cultural references, artistic impact

Literary translation presents unique challenges that distinguish it from other types of translation. Unlike technical or legal translation, which prioritizes precision and clarity, literary translation must capture the nuances, emotions, and stylistic elements of the original text. Cultural nuances, stylistic fidelity, emotional resonance, creative interpretation, and intertextual references highlight these challenges. The translation of proper names, as a type of literary translation, requires great skill from the translator.

In poetic translation, the art of bestowing distinctive appellations, which serve as primary vessels of national essence, holds significant sway. Generally, assigning special names in translation poses no grave challenge. The transliteration of original proper nouns into the alphabet of the translated language appears straightforward. Yet, it appears that in this nuanced realm, errors can seep in, detrimentally affecting the translation's fidelity to the original's cultural essence.

Anthroponyms, especially character names, play a crucial role in conveying meaning in literature. They not only serve as identifiers but also often carry connotations and cultural significance that can add depth to a narrative. When translating these names, the translator faces the challenge of maintaining both the denotative and connotative meanings. This task is complicated further when names have phonetic or symbolic resonance that is integral to the text's artistic effect.

The methodological challenge in translating anthroponyms lies in balancing fidelity to the original with readability and cultural resonance in the target language. Translators must decide whether to transliterate, translate, or adapt names based on their significance within the text. This decision-making process requires an understanding of the source culture, the target audience, and the literary context.

Specific names encapsulate the history, culture, traditions, and religious affiliations of their respective peoples in a singular manner, constituting a vital segment of the language's lexicon. As global interactions burgeon in the age of modern globalization, democratization, and widespread international connections, the role and significance of translation continue to ascend. Special names, encompassing anthroponyms and toponyms nestled within, exert considerable influence in transcending intercultural and interlinguistic barriers within the translation process.

The loss, whether semantic, graphic, or phonetic, of anthroponyms in literary translations, particularly in poetry, can lead them astray from their original essence, sometimes rendering them unrecognizable. Anthroponyms, intimately linked with national traditions, possess a profound connection to reality, making their preservation crucial. According to Lietz names themselves have a communicative value which is determined by three factors, namely *reference*, *meaning(fulness)* and an *aesthetic component* [4] (the latter being tantamount to what Newmark calls "euphony and elegance" [6]).

The onomastic units of the artistic text sometimes have a special importance in presenting and enlivening the artistic image, but also serve to create a national color. From this point of view, onomastic units attract attention with two contrasting features: the denotative meaning of words that are universal in terms of being understood in different languages and have a connotative meaning form the national and ethnocultural layer of the vocabulary. In a work of fiction, the words denoting the name of a person or a place as an image element reflect the characteristic aspects of the period and social life and have a number of "hidden" points: "The name of any character has a

number of connotations that can be understood only by having additional information about the circumstances" [5, p.7]. Therefore, although the issue of onomastic units during translation may seem simple at first glance, it requires special attention and a sensitive approach from the translator.

Azerbaijani poetry, rich in historical and cultural references, provides a compelling case study for examining the translation of personal names. Poets often use names to evoke particular historical periods, cultural contexts, and emotional responses. The translation of these names thus requires careful consideration to preserve the poem's essence and artistic impact.

The "Anthology of Poetry by Women in Azerbaijan: Classical to Soviet," [1] published in both Azerbaijani and English in 2014, illuminates the development of women's poetry in Azerbaijan, from the works of Mahseti Ganjavi to the poetry created during the Soviet period.

This collection provides a glimpse into the extensive range of poetry and lyrics created by women in this region. Many pieces are traditional love poems, with older works often initially composed as song lyrics. However, the themes also encompass nation, politics, culture, and work. Azerbaijan was a pioneer in the education of girls and women in the Muslim world and Central Asia, establishing numerous schools for girls in rural areas and the capital city of Baku during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. Consequently, women's literary output flourished from the nineteenth century onwards, frequently supported by educated patrons like the Karabagh poet Khurshidbanu Natavan, who hosted literary salons for both women and men in her home.

The anthology includes poetic samples rich with proper names. Here is an example by Gülsad (XVI-XVII century) and its translation:

Budur gəldi yesirlərin karvanı,
Çağırırım, ya Mövlana, ya Qəni,
Qara geydi əcəm pirü cavanı,
Bizdən salam olsun Əcəm elinə! [1, s. 21]

English translation:

Here comes a caravan of the unlucky ones —
I call to you: Hey, Məvlana! Hey Gani!
Young and old were dressed in black,
Give our regards to the land of Ajam!

The way of keeping fidelity to the original is transliteration of the proper names and providing footnotes to them. The footnote given at the bottom of the page about the special names used in the poem is as following: "Məvlana is a famous poet like Rumi, a Sufi mystic who lived in the thirteenth century." "Gani is one of the dervishes (a Sufi Muslim) who tried to extend Islam in Khorasan and Anatolia." "Melik is the title given to the provincial leaders of the Caliphate." [1, s. 22-23]

In general, "the role of proper names in the organization of the text in form and meaning has not yet been sufficiently studied. There is still a strong tendency to

look at specific names out of context". [9, p.105] However, this tendency to isolate specific names from their context does not compromise the quality of translation.

As is known, poets from the East, including those from Azerbaijan, frequently employ proper names in their works to convey particular ideas more emphatically. For instance, the legends of Leyli and Majnun, Farhad and Shirin, are widely circulated in the East, and these names frequently appear in various poems. They serve as symbols of certain philosophical positions and concepts of love.

An example from the poetry by Heyran Khanum (1790 – 1860) which includes proper names:

Səri-rivəşlə Xosrov sifət oturmaşdu,
Olubdu kuhdə Fərhad gördüyün könlüm. [1, s.32]
English translation:

There, on the marriage throne, sat one like Khosrow.

My own heart, you see, dwells in the mountains like Farhad's.

The translator provided an explanation of the special names in this piece of poetry at the end of the page:

"Farhad was a legendary figure who loved a princess, Shirin, who did not return his love. Instead, Shirin loved Khosrow."

In scholarly discourse concerning translation theory, discussions regarding the translation of proper names typically focus on the challenge of transcribing these names into the letter system of another language. However, alongside the conventional difficulties of practical transcription (transliteration) faced by translators, the question of the semantic representation of these names is equally significant. The comprehension of the conveyed information (and the imagery within the poem) often hinges on this issue.

As previously mentioned, proper names are typically rendered using the letters of the target language, resulting in the transcription (transliteration) of the given special name. Initially, this might seem straightforward, but a comparison of practical translations reveals certain complexities in providing transliterations of specific names.

Given that the utilization of personal names in literary works also contributes to the creation of imagery, this aspect should be duly considered in the translation process. Personal names, or anthroponyms, serve a nominative function in the language of literary works: "the author names a character to distinguish him from others. However, personal names in works of art also have an aesthetic effect. Sometimes the aesthetic function of the personal name comes to the fore: the hero's name plays the role of an artistic tool for revealing the image, the name reflects the character: if we are talking about a work in a foreign language, then the personal name can also play the role of strengthening the national color of the work". [10, p.138]

Translators who have translated examples of Azerbaijani poetry into English have predominantly endeavored to adhere to these principles. This effort is driven by the intention to convey the national essence reflected in the translated poems to English-speaking readers.

Regarding translating a piece of poetry brimming with delicate emotions into English without causing harm to its essence demands great competence from the translator. As Nigel Armstrong states, "While a bilingual translator with a very good knowledge of both cultures to which these languages belong can approach translation issues without any formal instruction, for individuals with less knowledge in the field the important and related aspects of these languages are it is necessary to conduct theoretical trainings related to These are the complete linguistic structure and cultural aspects of the languages of interest. The second aspect doubles the fact that both languages contain a number of cultural concepts that are radically different from each other, and at the same time, lexical units, which in many cases are difficult to determine the culture to which they belong, complicate the matter a bit. [2]

Our comparisons demonstrate that the omission or alteration of proper names in translations of Azerbaijani poetry into English results in the loss of national essence and significant meaning. Furthermore, it distorts the artistic style of the poets whose works are being translated. This is because "the writer's approach to the aesthetic function of the personal name often shapes their artistic style." [10, s.138]

An example from the poetry included into the so-called anthology by Mahsati Ganjavi:

Ey ağıllı qoca, deyilsən naşı,
Torpaq ələyən cavandır yaşı,
De, yavaş ələsin, çünki bu torpaq
Pərviz bədənidir, Keyqubad başı.(1, s. 9)

English translation:

Ay, wise old man, you are not unskilled.
The one who sifts the soil is too young —
tell him to work carefully, for this ground
is the body of Pərviz and the head of Keyqubad.

The two proper names included into the piece of poetry acquire not only literary, but also historical importance. Here is how the translator puts light on them: "Pərviz probably refers to Khosrau II, last king of the Sasanian empire in Persia, whose reign ended with the Muslim conquest of the region in the year 628. He is the historical basis of the fictional Khosrow in the widely read poetic saga Khosrow and Shirin by the Nizami Ganjavi (1149-1209)."

"Keyqubad likely refers to one of the Seljuq rulers. Given the presumed dates of the life of the poet Mahsati, it may refer to the first (1188-1237), though Mahsati would have been either born later or quite elderly to overlap with him. The remains of a mosque by this name, thought to have been built during the reign of Shirvanshah Keyqubad (1317-1356), were recently restored in the old city of Baku. The mosque, built after Mahsati's presumed lifetime, is part of the Shirvanshah's Palace in the old city of Baku, Azerbaijan."

Also, proper names are widely met in the poems by Khurshidbanu Natavan (1832 – 1897):

Yusifin sanma, dübarə görə Yəqub üzün,
Mehr bazarına gər getsə, Züleyxa gətirir.

Yusif Züleyxa Misirdə kər aldı nəqdə,
Nəqdi-can, aşiq olan, əldə mühəyya gətirir. [1, s.50]

English translation:

If Jacob hopes to see his dear Joseph again, he will bring Zuleykha —
only she can guide him through that lovers market.
In ancient Egypt, Zuleykha bought the deaf Joseph —
for even a slave can prepare for his lover's delight.
For Love you would sacrifice everything, Natavan.
Good news! He comes tonight, death's decree at his side.

The footnote says:" Leyla and Majnun is perhaps the most famous love story of this region, its most influential version written in verse by the poet Nizami (1141 – 1209) from the Ganja region of Azerbaijan. The first European style opera performed in the Middle East was based on this story. It was composed by Azerbaijani Uzeyir Hajibeyov. The Story of Zuleykha and the prophet Yusif (Joseph) is a favorite of love poetry"

Another example rich with proper names by Mashadi Khanum Leyli (1892 – 1912) included into the anthology:

Füzundur Leylidən, Şirindən, Əzradan ənduhim,
Mənim Fərhədü Qeysim, Vamiqi Sənanım ayrıldı.
Nə noi səbr edim hicranına Məcnunun, ey Leyli,
Həyatım, ruhum ayrıldı, şəhim, sultanım ayrıldı.
[1, s. 81]

English translation:

My grief surpasses that of Layla, Shirin, and Azra —
My Farhadi-Qeys, my own Vamigi-Sanan has left me.
Ay, Leyli, how can I live with the loss of Majnun?
My soul and my spirit, my King and my sultan have left me.

The used proper names in the poetical piece are explained in the footnotes: "All three are legendary heroines who suffered for love. Three are the names of legendary men who (at times) love the heroines Shirin (Farhad), Layla (Qeys—he is later renamed Majnun, after his love-sickness), and Azra (Vamiq). Sanan is the name of a legendary Muslim Sheikh who fell in love with a Christian (perhaps Georgian) woman. The particular joining of these heroic male lovers' names, one as an adjective, the other as a noun, serves as an intensification of the desirable but problematic male lover.

Legendary lover of the heroine Layla – a name similar in sound to the poet's name Leyli."

"Translation is partly a science and partly an art, I would say also a craft and a matter of taste. I think science is the search for truth – this is an old-fashioned word in Translation Studies. To me the scientific aspect

is, above all, non-literary, it's about things, it's about reality, it's about facts, it's impersonal, and it's about objects. The other is the aesthetic, or, if you like, translation as an art, and this is imagination, which is so important. This is beauty, this is literary translation, this centres on people, as literature does." [5, p.14]

In translation theory, discussions on the transliteration of proper names often focus on transferring these names to another language's letter system. However, beyond practical transcription and transliteration challenges, the semantic presentation of these names is crucial for comprehension.

"Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" epic is a historical monument that provides rich historical materials about the life, beliefs, and living areas of the Oguz people, as well as their relations with neighbors. But, in English translation of the "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" saga, the tendency to look at proper names out of context is less apparent. This is understandable, as the epic is deeply rooted in national and historical contexts, and the characters cannot be separated from their settings. To convey these images effectively, it is essential to capture the spirit of the epic in the translation.

Researches on different translations of the "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" epic reveals that proper names are mostly transliterated or transcribed. However, inconsistencies exist where the same names appear differently in various translations and even within the same translation, which harms the quality of the work.

The first comprehensive English translation of "Kitabi-Dade Korgud," titled "The Book of Dede Korkut," was published in the USA in 1972 by Faruk Sumer, Ahmed Uysal, and Warren Walker, the epic was simply presented as "Dede Korkut," with the name given in parentheses as "Book of My Grandfather Korkut." [7]

As seen from the provided examples, transliteration of proper names in translation is a widely approved method. However, it should also consider the cultural context, metaphorical meaning, and emotions of the source text, based on the golden rules of translation emphasized by experts. "...translation is an interpretative art, a scientific process, a skill of rewriting in which the contents of Source Language (SL) are reproduced into Target Language (TL). This reproduction should be very close to the meaning of SL where sense is usually maintained. The identities of culture, thematic, metaphorical, pragmatic and linguistic elements of Source Language should preferably be given due importance while recreating it into Target Language (TL). [3, p.21]

It is generally accepted by translation experts that, it is crucial to accurately include proper names in translations to adhere to the norms of literary language. However, this necessity is often overlooked, resulting in a disregard for the original literary language norms. Consequently, this oversight not only distorts the literary language but also dilutes the national essence conveyed in the original text. The significance lies in the fact that while proper names may not always serve as

semantic markers within the structure of a literary work, their semantic content and phonetic qualities contribute to conveying specific artistic and poetic nuances, thus defining the distinct character and ethos of the literary piece as a whole.

Translation of proper names, particularly anthroponyms, in literature is a complex task that requires a nuanced approach. Translators must navigate between preserving the original's cultural and emotional weight and making the text accessible to readers in the target language. This balancing act is essential to maintaining the integrity and beauty of literary works across linguistic boundaries.

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